

Response of rainfed wetland rice to level, method, and timing of azolla application

G.L. Gregorio, A.L. Leccio, and A. Ofalla, Panay State Polytechnic College, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines

We conducted two azolla experiments under rainfed conditions during the 1983 crop year. The first involved two application methods (Table 1) in split-plot design with three replications. Fresh azolla was incorporated and surface-applied at 0, 10, 20, and 30 t/ha. IR36 was grown on 2- × 3-m plots at 25- × 25-cm spacing with practices suitable for rainfed culture. Partially sun-dried azolla was applied 3 d before transplanting.

The second experiment involved seven timings of azolla application (Table 2) in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Azolla was incorporated at 20 t/ha, IR36 was spaced 25 × 25 cm with 3 seedlings/ hill.

Method of application did not affect plant height, tiller count, fresh straw yield, 1000-seed weight, or the grain yield (Table 1). Taller plants occurred in all azolla-treated plots. Highest grain yield (7.0 t/ha) was with 20 t azolla/ ha.

Time of treatment did not influence height and fresh straw yield (Table 2). Azolla applied 2 WBT had the most tillers (17/hill). Applying azolla 3 WBT, 2 WBT, 1 WBT, or ATT was evidently best for grain yield; means ranged from 6.6 to 7.8 t/ha. Grain yields decreased significantly when application was after transplanting. □

Table 1. Effect of 2 application methods and 4 rates of fresh azolla on growth and yield of IR36. PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Application method	Application rate (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/hill (av no.)	Fresh straw wt (t/ha)	1000-seed wt (g)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Surface applied	0	77.5	13	17.8	25.8	5.9
	10	87.1	15	15.2	26.4	6.7
	20	85.1	15	12.9	25.3	6.7
	30	87.0	15	14.0	27.5	6.5
Incorporated	0	81.4	13	13.7	25.8	6.5
	10	85.7	15	14.4	27.5	6.9
	20	84.4	15	15.4	26.9	7.2
	30	84.2	14	13.0	28.1	6.5
Means (rate)	0	79.4	13	15.7	25.8	6.2
	10	86.4	15	14.8	26.9	6.8
	20	84.7	15	14.2	26.1	7.0
	30	85.6	15	13.5	21.8	6.5
Means (method)	Surface applied	84.2	15	15.0	26.2	6.5
	Incorporated	83.9	14	14.1	27.1	6.8
Test of significance	Method	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	Level	1%	ns	5%	ns	5%
	Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
LSD (for level)	5%	4.5	—	1.7	—	0.7
	1%	6.4	—	2.4	—	1.0
CV (%)	Main plot	3.6	6.6	12.8	10.0	1.3
	Sub-plot	3.0	8.5	7.2	5.6	6.1

^a Sun-dried weight.

Table 2. Time of azolla application and growth and yield components of IR36.^a PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Time of application ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Fresh straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
3 WBT	71.0	14 b	15.0	7.6 a
2 WBT	75.5	17 a	15.7	7.8 a
1 WBT	71.3	14 b	15.1	6.8 ab
ATT	70.0	13 b	14.9	6.6 abc
1 WT	70.7	12 b	14.7	5.6 bcd
2 WT	70.9	11 b	14.3	5.3 cd
3 WT	69.2	11 b	13.9	4.7 d
Test of significance	—	1%	—	1%
cv (%)	6.8	9.1	4.8	13.6

^a Means of 4 replications. In a column, means with a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bWBT = weeks before transplanting, ATT = at transplanting, WT = weeks after transplanting. ^c Sun-dried weight.

Effect of Zn on yield and quality of rice in Turkey

I. Karaçal, University of Ankara, Faculty of Agriculture, Turkey; and M. Teceren, Institute of Variety Testing and Registration, Ankara, Turkey

The effect of Zn applied with N and P on grain yield and quality of rice

grown in the main production areas of Turkey was studied. Field experiments in Central Anatolia, Çorum Province, Ankara, and at Trachia, Edirne Province, lasted 2 yr. Soil analyses of the experimental fields are shown in Table I. Seven different treatments were tested with rice variety Ribe in a randomized block design replicated four times. Treatments are in Table 2.

Urea and superphosphate were applied at 150 kg N/ha and 35 kg P/ha to all treatments.

ZnSO₄ · 7H₂O at 60 kg should be applied to the soil before seeding in Çorum; in the other states, foliar application of ZnSO₄ gave better results.

One rice quality factor is protein content. Zn had no effect on protein

Table 1. Physical and chemical properties of ricefield soils in Turkey.

State	Soil depth (cm)	Texture ^a	pH	Organic matter (%)	CaCO ₃ (%)	Total N (%)	Available Olsen P (ppm)	Exchangeable cations (meq/100 g)				CEC (meq/100 g)	DTPA extractable			
								Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺		Zn (ppm)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Cu (ppm)
Corum	0-20	C	7.4	1.41	9.45	1.36	6.94	1.88	0.42	22.00	9.88	34.18	2.03	41.10	12.72	7.05
	20-40	C	7.5	1.54	10.12	1.06	6.24	1.40	0.46	20.16	8.00	30.02	1.09	42.20	12.27	11.43
	40-60	C	7.3	1.61	9.88	0.94	3.18	0.96	0.31	18.40	11.13	30.80	0.48	40.13	12.00	9.00
Ankara	0-20	C	7.6	2.65	22.23	1.49	7.28	0.34	1.39	26.16	9.13	37.02	2.96	45.00	13.88	5.45
	20-40	C	7.7	1.13	22.37	1.47	3.04	0.20	1.46	24.24	10.37	36.27	3.02	41.00	8.74	8.00
	40-60	C	7.7	2.46	22.00	1.45	4.32	0.12	1.63	13.90	10.00	25.65	2.88	32.86	11.62	5.20
Edirne	0-20	Sil	6.6	1.14	1.52	1.71	7.62	1.32	0.63	10.38	7.10	19.43	1.08	56.25	14.64	2.58
	20-40	Sil	7.0	0.40	11.66	1.43	7.62	0.88	0.36	12.24	6.40	19.88	0.39	40.14	11.12	1.74
	40-60	Sil	7.2	0.34	1.08	1.06	5.30	0.97	0.30	8.20	4.16	13.63	0.45	42.00	12.88	1.11

^a C = clayey, Sil = silty.

Table 2. Effect of Zn on grain yield in Turkey.

Treatment	1981 crop season				1982 crop season				Mean yield (t/ha)	Mean increase (%)
	Corum		Ankara		Corum		Edirne			
	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)		
No Zn	4.6 cd	—	3.4 b	—	3.5	—	6.7	—	4.5	—
30 kg ZnSO ₄ basal	5.6 ab	20.9	4.4 ab	30.1	3.8	7.3	7.2	7.2	5.2	15.0
60 kg ZnSO ₄ basal	5.7 a	23.5	4.4 ab	31.0	4.3	21.1	7.1	5.8	5.4	17.9
1% ZnSO ₄ foliar	4.8 bcd	4.0	5.1 a	49.0	3.9	11.9	7.5	11.9	5.3	16.8
1% Zn-EDDHA foliar	5.4 abc	16.6	3.7 b	7.6	3.6	1.5	6.5	-2.7	5.8	4.9
1% ZnSO ₄ seed soak	5.0 abcd	8.3	3.6 b	5.1	3.6	2.6	6.9	2.5	4.8	4.5
ZnO seed coat	4.4 d	-5.1	4.3 ab	25.3	4.0	12.9	6.8	1.8	4.8	6.6
SD	47.3		72.8		47.1		62.4			
CV (%)	9.0		17.7		12.4		9.0			
F	**		*		ns		ns			

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level.

content. Milling recovery increased 67-70% in Corum, 61-66% in Ankara, and 58-62% in Edirne, regardless of Zn applications; the variation was not

significant. The 1000-kernel wt also showed no difference.

A common Zn deficiency exists in the rice production area of Corum.

Farmers have recognized the problem, but thought it a disease, not a nutritional problem. Application of Zn will solve it. □

Effect of Calcutta City waste compost on rice yield

N. Chattopadhyay, M. D. Gupta, and S. K. Gupta, University College of Agriculture, Calcutta University, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta 700019, West Bengal, India

Disposal of city garbage is a continuing problem in Calcutta. Dumping lands are gradually being filled up by city garbage and further dumping is almost impossible. Newly developed, expensive land is being used as garbage dumps, wasting

material wealth and posing health hazards.

Wastes could be converted to compost and used for agricultural purposes. Investigations at the Agricultural Experimental Farm during 1984 and 1985 kharif examined

the possibility of using such compost alone or in combination with urea in rice production.

Characteristics of soil and Calcutta city waste compost, mechanically prepared, are presented in Table 1. N at 120 kg/ha was supplied by urea,

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of soil and compost. Calcutta, India.

	pH	Organic C (%)	Available nutrients (ppm)						
			N	P	K	Zn	Mn	Fe	Cu
Soil	6.2	0.92	94.0	20.3	520.8	0.82	0.55	4.22	0.15
Calcutta City waste compost	8.1	7.50	343.3	374.0	2185.0	147.05	35.00	89.25	29.25